

Development of a Non-Iterative Artificial Neural Network Model for Enhanced Finite Element Analysis of Short Fiber-Reinforced Plastics

2025.8.6

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Introduction

Short fiber-reinforced plastics (SFRPs)

Classification of fiber reinforcement

Industrial application of SFRP

Advanced Functional Materials 32.40 (2022) 2205723

Anisotropic mechanical behavior of SFRPs

Injection molding process

Manufacturing Techniques for PMCs (2012)

Variation of microstructure

Computational Mechanics 61 (2018) 729-750

Anisotropic dependence on mechanical behavior

Composites: Part A 73 (2015) 166-175

- Tensile behavior of SFRP has strong dependence on local anisotropy induced by injection molding process.
- Mechanical behavior prediction method maintaining high accuracy and low computation cost is necessary for properly using SFRP in industrial field.

Prediction of the static failure behavior of SFRP Parts

How can we predict the mechanical failure behavior of this anisotropic composite?

Mechanical models for SFRPs

Phenomenological models

European Journal of Mechanics-A/Solids 29(6) (2010) 1065-1077

International Journal of Fatigue 136 (2020) 105571

- Require labor-intensive experiments to characterize the fatigue properties considering the properties of constituents (fiber volume fraction, aspect ratio or orientation tensor).
- → **Difficult for modeling SFRP parts** that have significantly different mechanical properties due to varying the **local fiber orientation**.

Micromechanical models

International Journal of Fatigue 160 (2022) 106880

- Describe the fatigue failure of SFRPs considering individual constituents (fiber, matrix, and interface).
- → **Time-intensive** because stress calculation of all fibers, matrix and interfaces is enormous.

Two-step homogenization for SFRPs

Thesis Ecole Polytechnique de Louvain 61 (2019)

1. **Pseudograin decomposition:** Gommers (1998), Weber (1999), Ogierman (2017)
2. **1st Homogenization:** Mori-Tanaka (1973)

$$\langle C \rangle_{\Omega} = [(1 - v_i)C_m + v_i C_i : A^{\varepsilon}] : [(1 - v_i)I + v_i A^{\varepsilon}]^{-1}$$

$$A^{\varepsilon}_{MT} = [I + S : (C_m^{-1} : C_i - I)]^{-1}$$
3. **2nd homogenization:** Voigt (1889)

$$\langle C \rangle_{\Omega} = [(1 - v_i)C_m + v_i C_i]$$

- **Two step homogenization method** was suggested to predict the mechanical behavior of SFRPs considering the **local orientation** and **computational cost**.
- Two-step homogenization is composed of following procedures.
 - Pseudograin decomposition: Gommers (1998), Weber (1999), Ogierman (2017)
 - 1st Homogenization: Mori-Tanaka (1973), Miller (2013)
 - 2nd Homogenization: Voigt (1889)
- DIGIMAT software allowed static failure prediction by using two-step homogenization, but failure behavior prediction showed high dependence on **user-defined failed weight fraction of entire pseudograin**.

We decided to develop ABAQUS user material subroutine (UMAT)

Based on two-step homogenization framework utilizing pseudograin approach.

Fiber - elastic

$\langle \Delta \varepsilon_f \rangle$

$$\langle \Delta \varepsilon_f \rangle = B: [v_f B + v_m I]^{-1}: \langle \Delta \varepsilon \rangle$$

Matrix - viscoelastic viscoplastic

$\langle \Delta \varepsilon_m \rangle$

$$\langle \Delta \varepsilon_m \rangle = [v_f B + v_m I]^{-1}: \langle \Delta \varepsilon \rangle$$

Mori-Tanaka 1st homogenization

$\langle \Delta \sigma \rangle_{PG1 \sim 12}$

$$C_{PG} = [v_m C_m + v_f C_f: B^\varepsilon]: [v_f B + v_m I]^{-1}$$

$$\Delta \sigma_{PG} = C_{PG}: \Delta \varepsilon_{PG}$$

What are the main obstacles to achieve our goal?

Nested loop structure in 2-step homogenization algorithm

✓ 2-step homogenization using the pseudograin approach involves nested loops for calculation.

→ The excessive number of iterations leads to increased computational time and lower vectorization efficiency.

ANN-based constitutive equation

- ✓ Need to fully capture and understand the constitutive behavior of materials
- ✓ Iterative calculations to model non-linear plastic deformation

- ✓ Highly nonlinear regression method predicting response without explicit function expressions
- ✓ Reduces the number of iterations and enhance vectorization efficiency

Initial approach: Modular ANN Architecture

Modularize each loop instead of creating multiple loops all at once.

1. Easy to focus on each system's physics, making pattern recognition and learning more effective.
2. Easy to modify each model when system changes occur, such as material changes.

Modular ANN (1): return mapping

Modular ANN (1): return mapping

CPU calculation time for each algorithm

	Return mapping	ANN	Reduction rate
1000 elements	111 sec	108 sec	3 %
loop only	2.9 msec	1.6 msec	55 %

- ✓ Specimen level simulation showed both methods achieve high accuracy.
- ✓ The ANN model achieved a 55% reduction at the loop level, but only about 3% across the full 1000-element analysis.

Modular ANN (2): Mori-Tanaka homogenization ANN

- ✓ Error accumulation occurs due to the consecutive use of two neural networks.
- ✓ Since accurate prediction requires the output of one ANN as input for the other, using the first ANN's output as input was challenging.

Alternative strategy: Integrated ANN

- ✓ Instead of sequentially connecting neural networks, a single integrated neural network that can simultaneously represent both systems is needed.

Mori-Tanaka iteration loop

- To estimate the macroscopic behavior of pseudo grain, the Mori–Tanaka homogenization method is used.
- Repeat until convergence:
 - a. Decompose pseudo grain strain into matrix and fiber strain
 - b. Update plastic matrix stress and elastic fiber stress
 - c. Update average stiffness and recompute matrix strain
 - d. Check convergence of matrix and fiber strain
- As a result, pseudo-grain level stiffness and stress are computed analytically.

Problem when using Integrated ANN

What we need is...

- ✓ The ANN is designed to approximate Mori–Tanaka homogenization by mapping pseudo-grain strain to stress increment and tangent stiffness.
- ✓ However, directly using full 3D stress and stiffness tensors as ANN outputs makes the network excessively large and computationally inefficient.

→ Need to reduce input and output features

Strategy for integrated ANN (1): output feature

Knowing the matrix's **effective plastic strain** ($\bar{\varepsilon}_{mat}^p$) allows determination of $\Delta \varepsilon_{mat}$ and $\Delta \varepsilon_{fib}$.

Calculate matrix's stress and stiffness

$$\sigma_{mat} = \mathbf{C} : \Delta \varepsilon_{mat} - 2\mu \Delta \bar{\varepsilon}^p \mathbf{N}^{trial}$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{mat}^{alg} = \tilde{\mathbf{E}} - \frac{(2\tilde{G})^2}{h_v} \mathbf{N} \otimes \mathbf{N} - (2\tilde{G})^2 \frac{\sigma_{eq} \Delta \bar{\varepsilon}^p}{\sigma_{eq} + 3\tilde{G} \Delta \bar{\varepsilon}^p} \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}}{\partial \sigma}$$

- C_{pg} using rule of mixture
- Damaged stiffness and stress

\therefore The ANN requires only $\bar{\varepsilon}_{mat}^p$ as output.

Strategy for integrated ANN (2): input features

Prior effective plastic strain of matrix

- ✓ Need to monitor the degree of plastic strain.
- Use the effective plastic strain from the previous increment.

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \varepsilon_{ij}^p \varepsilon_{ij}^p}$$

Von-Mises pseudo-grain effective strain

- ✓ Need to provide scalar input for yield evaluation and plastic strain increment
- Use von Mises equivalent strain derived from pseudo-grain level strain

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\varepsilon} &= \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \varepsilon_{\text{dev}} : \varepsilon_{\text{dev}}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} [(\varepsilon_{xx} - \varepsilon_{yy})^2 + (\varepsilon_{yy} - \varepsilon_{zz})^2 + (\varepsilon_{zz} - \varepsilon_{xx})^2 + 6(\varepsilon_{xy}^2 + \varepsilon_{yz}^2 + \varepsilon_{zx}^2)]} \end{aligned}$$

Final ANN structure

$$(\bar{\varepsilon}_{mat}^{p,n}) = f_{\text{ANN-2}} \left(\hat{\varepsilon}_{pg}, \bar{\varepsilon}_{mat}^{p,n-1} \right)$$

→ Two scalar values are used as input to predict one scalar output.

Dataset for integrated ANN (1)

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11}x + \epsilon_{12}y + \epsilon_{31}z \\ \epsilon_{22}y + \epsilon_{12}x + \epsilon_{23}z \\ \epsilon_{33}z + \epsilon_{23}y + \epsilon_{31}x \end{bmatrix}$$

Viscoplastic parameter	
Yield stress (MPa), σ_y	32.91
Hardening exponent, B	0.5446
Hardening modulus, C	39.35
Viscoplastic coefficient, η	6481
Viscoplastic exponent, VN	1.48

Fiber properties	
Elastic modulus (GPa)	72.0
Poisson ratio	0.22
Density (g/cm ³)	1.80
Fiber volume fraction	0.208 ($\approx W_f : 0.4$)
Fiber aspect ratio	25

Dataset with various loading path

Longitudinal tension
Transverse tension
Longitudinal pure shear
Biaxial tension + shear
Biaxial mixed load + shear
biaxial compression + shear
...

- ✓ Finite element simulations with 100 increments were used to generate each database.
- ✓ Various loading paths were considered under a simple linear loading condition.

Dataset for integrated ANN (2)

	#	ϵ_{11}	ϵ_{22}	ϵ_{33}	ϵ_{12}	ϵ_{31}	ϵ_{23}
Longitudinal tension	1	0.04	0	free	0	0	0
Transverse tension	2	0	0.06	free	0	0	0
Longitudinal pure shear	3	0	0	0	0.06	0	0
Biaxial load with shear	4	0.02	0.024	free	0.06	0	0
	5	-0.02	0.03	free	0.045	0	0
	6	0.016	-0.04	free	0.05	0	0
	7	0.016	0.04	free	0.04	0	0
	8	0.02	0.06	free	0.04	0	0
	9	0.016	0.06	free	0.03	0	0
	10	0.016	0.06	free	0.02	0	0
	11	-0.02	-0.02	free	0.06	0	0
	12	-0.02	-0.04	free	0.04	0	0
	13	-0.02	-0.06	free	0.02	0	0
Test loading set 1	14	0.02	0.036	free	0.027	0	0
	15	-0.02	-0.04	free	0.027	0	0
	16	0.02	0.075	free	0.03	0	0
Test loading set 2	17	0.02	0.02	free	0.06	0	0
	18	0.02	0.04	free	0.04	0	0.02
	19	0.02	0.03	free	0.03	0	0.03

13 random loading path for training

→ 1300 training datasets were generated.

Training integrated ANN

Hyperparameter search: hyperband algorithm

Hyperband

Prediction test

- ✓ In order to find the appropriate hyperparameter of ANN such as the number of neurons and hidden layers, hyperband algorithm was used.
- ✓ The predicted and actual values plot of output variables showed remarkably high accuracy with an R-squared value of over 0.9999

Mori-Tanka ANN test results

Test results (loading path #14~17)

→ Test dataset within the training range.

Test results (loading path #18~19)

→ 23-direction strain not included in training was used.

- ✓ The neural network shows high accuracy within the training range.
- ✓ The use of effective strain enables accurate predictions even when shear components not included in training are applied.

ABAQUS User Subroutine(UMAT) implementation results

Loading beyond the training range

$$\{\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}, \varepsilon_{33}, \varepsilon_{12}, \varepsilon_{13}, \varepsilon_{23}\} = \{0.05, 0, \text{free}, \varepsilon_3, 0, 0\}$$

Non-proportional loading

→ The loading path was altered through multiple steps

- ✓ The trained neural network was implemented and tested using an ABAQUS user-defined subroutine (UMAT).
- ✓ The model performs well beyond the training domain, effectively handling even non-proportional loading cases.

Calculation time comparison (1): multi-element test

Single pseudo grain test (1000 elements)

7.5% reduction

12 pseudo grain test (1000 elements)

33% reduction

- ✓ Computational time was reduced by employing neural networks, especially in cases involving 12 pseudo-grains.
- ✓ This reduction is expected to become more significant as the number of elements increases.

Concluding remarks

Non-iterative artificial neural network constitutive model

- ANN-based constitutive model to predict the properties of polymer matrix and combined fiber composite materials was developed.
- The proposed ANN successfully approximates Mori–Tanaka homogenization with high accuracy, even under loading conditions beyond the training domain.
- By reducing computational cost, the ANN demonstrates strong potential for integration into large-scale finite element simulations.

Thank you very much for your attention
